

Reframing the Disruption index by incorporating citation intentions

Xin Xie*, and Jiang Li*

*502022140049@smail.nju.edu.cn; lijiang@nju.edu.cn

0009-0009-7747-8292; 0000-0001-5769-8647

School of Information Management, Nanjing University, China

Abstract

This study proposes a feasible framework to combine the disruption index with citation intentions to further understand the progress of scientific advances. Our analyses are mainly based on the Semantic Scholar Academic Graph dataset, which provides classified intentions of background information, methodology and result comparison. In order to ensure the assessment accuracy, we focus on papers published from 1969 to 2019 and investigate the distributions and trends of both the three original indexes measuring disruption and the nine variants with intents. The results verify the claim that science is becoming less disruptive both from the overall perspective and from the viewpoint of three citing intentions. And we also prove the convergent validity of the disruption variants with intents through calculating Spearman rank correlations.

1. Introduction

Previously, in order to detect scientific breakthrough and outline the structure of research fields, scholars mainly focused on the magnitude of a publication's later use to quantify its impact, such as the citation count (Gross & Gross, 1927). However, these one-dimensional citation impact measurements (Bu et al., 2019) overlook the fact that new technologies are related to pre-existing ones, i.e., the previous accumulated knowledge enables the emerging and progressing of new technologies (Funk & Owen-Smith, 2017). Therefore, nowadays multi-dimensional indicators using techniques like co-citation analysis and bibliographic coupling are developed and widely used to reveal the breadth and depth of impact (Bu et al., 2019), such as indicators of creativity (Fleming, 2001; Lee et al., 2015), novelty (Uzzi et al., 2013), originality (Shibayama & Wang, 2020), consolidation and destabilization (Funk & Owen-Smith, 2017), and disruptiveness (Wu et al., 2019).

The concept of “disruptiveness” can be traced back to the idea of “disruptive technology” introduced by Christensen. It refers to the kinds of technology which are inferior in the main attributes valued by mainstream consumers, but focus on certain neglected attributes alternatively, thereby slowly surpassing and replacing the dominant technologies in the market (Bower & Christensen, 1996; Christensen, 1997; Christensen & Bower, 1996). Capturing the idea of “disruptive technology” and “scientific revolutions” (Kuhn & Hawkins, 1963), Funk & Owen-Smith (2017) proposed the CD (Consolidation and Destabilization) index, quantifying the degree to which a new innovation consolidates or destabilizes the subsequent use of existing technologies. A destabilizing invention would decrease the citations of its predecessors since it overthrows established thinking and reshapes networks of interlinked technologies. Conversely, a consolidating invention would increase citations of the technologies upon which it builds since it follows previous research lines. Subsequently, Wu et al. (2019) proposed the Disruption index based on the CD index. It aims to evaluate the disruptive potential of a scientific publication in its field through assessing the degree to which it eclipses attention to its previous

work. And several variants of the Disruption index have also been proposed to improve its flaws (Bornmann et al., 2020; Leydesdorff et al., 2021; Wu & Yan, 2019).

It is potentially problematic to utilize citation counts in research evaluation without considering citation contexts, since not all references carry the same level of importance (Nicholson et al., 2021), and various meanings exist for why specific articles are cited (Bornmann & Daniel, 2008; Tahamtan & Bornmann, 2019). However, the simple counting of citations fails to provide insight into what section authors are targeting at, let alone the motivation of their citing behaviour (Brooks, 1985; Roman et al., 2021b). Authors' citation intentions, referring to the purpose of the citation or the reason for citing particular reference (Lahiri et al., 2023; Roman et al., 2021a, 2021b), may be totally different in their research work (Garfield, 1998). Besides, since the citing behaviour of authors is primarily affected by professional motivations, citation intentions are deemed to be reliable for scientometric assessment (Vinkler, 1987). Early in 1978, Kochen (1978) has suggested to combine citation counts with citation content to improve the indicators of publication quality. Recent researches have also shown that the proportions of citation intentions differ not only in highly-cited papers and lowly-cited papers (Case & Higgins, 2000), but also in different sections of the articles (Maričić et al., 1998).

It is interesting and crucial to differentiate the role of distinct cited references based on authors' citing behaviours and to examine the degree to which they contribute to science advances in their respective roles. Nevertheless, to the best of our knowledge, none of the existing indicators measuring science progress has taken citation intents into consideration. To fill this gap, our research attempts to propose a feasible framework to integrate the disruption index with the citation intentions, as well as investigating the distributions and trends of both the original indexes measuring disruption and the variants with citation intents.

2. Data and measurements

2.1. Dataset and sample selection

In the study, we employed the Semantic Scholar Academic Graph (S2AG) dataset (accessible at <https://www.semanticscholar.org/product/api>), which contains the basic bibliographic metadata of 205,770,870 papers published by 79 million authors from 1931 to 2020, along with 2.49 billion citation data among these papers. The citation data provide information on citation intents, which are categorized into three types through the classification approach proposed by Cohan et al. (2019). Specifically, the “background information” denotes citations that provide more context about a problem, concept, approach, topic, or the importance of a problem, the “method” intention refers to utilizing previously established method, tool, approach or dataset of the cited work, and the “result comparison” represents citations that compare and extend the results or findings of early publications. Notably, the citation intent data is restricted to papers with full-text accessible since the context is required for intention prediction (Cohan et al., 2019). Consequently, around 1.4 billion pieces of citation data do not have citation intents, accounting for approximately 70% of the citation data.

We then excluded publications with zero citations or year information missing from the sample. Besides, since records before the 1960s are sparse and do not have strictly regulated references, we only included papers published between 1969 and 2019 to ensure reliable data. This also retains a citation window for at least 3 years for accurate assessments (Bornmann & Tekles, 2019a, 2019b).

2.2. The original Disruption index and its variants

The Disruption index was developed by Wu et.al (2019) and the formula for calculating the disruptiveness of a focal paper (FP for short) can be expressed as **Equation (1)**,

$$DI = \frac{N_i - N_j}{N_i + N_j + N_k} \quad (1)$$

where N_i is the number of papers citing the FP without citing any of its cited references, N_j is the number of papers citing both the FP and at least one of its references, and N_k is the number of papers which are published after the FP and cite at least one of the FP's references without citing the FP itself. A paper may be disruptive ($DI > 0$), neutral ($DI = 0$) or developing ($DI < 0$).

Additionally, our research utilizes two alternative improved variants, which exclude N_k from the calculation. One is the variant briefly mentioned in Wu et al. (2019) (**Equation (2)**), and the other is proposed by Wu & Yan (2019) (**Equation (3)**).

$$DI_{nok} (Wu \text{ et.al,2019}) = \frac{N_i}{N_i + N_j} \quad (2)$$

$$DI_{nok} (Wu \& Yan,2019) = \frac{N_i - N_j}{N_i + N_j} \quad (3)$$

We incorporated these three indexes in our empirical portion, and a simplified depiction of them is shown in **Figure 1**. In later sections, the three indexes are abbreviated as follows: DI for DI , DI_{nok1} for $DI_{nok} (Wu \text{ et.al., 2019})$, and DI_{nok2} for $DI_{nok} (Wu \& Yan, 2019)$. Notably, the indicators of DI and DI_{nok2} measure disruptiveness on a continuous scale from -1 to 1, whereas DI_{nok1} ranges from 0 to 1.

Figure 1: Simplified illustration of the Disruption index and its variants. The citation network comprises a focal paper (a blue diamond), references of the focal paper (grey circles) and subsequent works (rectangles). Subsequent works may cite the focal work (i , green), cite both the focal work and its references (j , orange) or just cite its references (k , red).

2.3. New variants of the Disruption index integrating citation intentions

We proposed a new set of variants of the Disruption index by integrating three citation intents, including background information, methodology and result comparison, respectively. Taking

And their abbreviations in later chapters go as follows: *db*, *db_nok1*, *db_nok2*, *dr*, *dr_nok1*, and *dr_nok2*.

Besides, our study also includes two citation impact indicators, including the number of citations of the literature until the end of 2022 (*Citation*), and its time-normalized citation counts (*Standard Citation*), i.e., the number of citations received per year from its publication year to the end of 2022.

3. Results

3.1. Descriptive results

Table 1 reports the descriptive statistics for values of the three original indexes in **Equations (1), (2) and (3)**, the nine disruption variants incorporating citation intents, and the two citation impact indicators from 1969 to 2019. Wu et al. (2019) claimed that *DI* is undefined when neither the focal paper nor its predecessors has been cited by subsequent publications ($N_i = N_j = N_k = 0$). The same is true of the other two disruption indexes *DI_nok1* and *DI_nok2* ($N_i = N_j = 0$). From the mathematical perspective, this actually excludes papers whose disruptiveness are incalculable since the denominator in the expression equals zero. Therefore, we also exclude incalculable papers for variants with intents from our reporting results respectively (e.g., $N_{im} = N_{jm} = N_{km} = 0$ for *DI_m*), thus the number of observations differs among variables.

Table 1. Descriptive statistics of the variables.

Variable	Obs.	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max
DI	78,276,933	0.340	0.472	-1	1
DI_nok1	78,125,490	0.625	0.381	0	1
DI_nok2	78,125,490	0.250	0.761	-1	1
db	54,584,008	0.550	0.491	-1	1
db_nok1	49,883,325	0.840	0.296	0	1
db_nok2	49,883,325	0.680	0.593	-1	1
dm	37,922,218	0.372	0.476	-1	1
dm_nok1	26,091,380	0.850	0.304	0	1
dm_nok2	26,091,380	0.699	0.607	-1	1
dr	30,283,773	0.261	0.430	-1	1
dr_nok1	14,715,917	0.879	0.284	0	1
dr_nok2	14,715,917	0.757	0.567	-1	1
Citation	78,497,280	24.949	141.137	1	265,410
Standard Citation	78,497,280	1.686	9.564	0.020	29,490

The average values of the three original indexes are much larger than those in previous studies. We suspect these abnormal mean values may be attributed to the lack of reference records in most of the literature. Therefore, we further report the statistics excluding papers with zero references (**Table 2**). As shown, the mean values of the three original indexes decrease sharply, while the declines of the variants incorporating intents are smaller due to the differences in calculation criteria. Specifically, in the calculation process of the latter, citations involved are restricted to those with corresponding intents and irrelevant citations are excluded. Consequently, even though a paper has references, the value of the disruption variant with intent may still be 1.000. Notably, the maximum values of *Citation* and *Standard Citation* also decrease, indicating papers with zero references may have high citations. These papers could

actually be highly disruptive in their fields as their works might break the framework of predecessors and be widely acknowledged by later researchers. Since the exclusion of these papers may lead to more severe bias, our later analysis still includes papers with zero references.

Table 2. Descriptive statistics of the variables (excluding papers with zero references).

Variable	Obs.	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max
DI	52,862,513	0.023	0.140	-1	1
DI_nok1	52,711,074	0.444	0.338	0	1
DI_nok2	52,711,074	-0.112	0.675	-1	1
db	42,677,404	0.424	0.486	-1	1
db_nok1	37,976,765	0.790	0.324	0	1
db_nok2	37,976,765	0.580	0.648	-1	1
dm	33,719,944	0.294	0.446	-1	1
dm_nok1	21,889,198	0.821	0.323	0	1
dm_nok2	21,889,198	0.642	0.647	-1	1
dr	28,169,015	0.205	0.393	-1	1
dr_nok1	12,601,257	0.858	0.302	0	1
dr_nok2	12,601,257	0.716	0.603	-1	1
Citation	52,872,449	30.764	146.515	1	226,120
Standard Citation	52,872,449	2.204	9.787	0.020	16,657

We further investigate the distributions of the 12 disruption measures separately (**Figure 3**). Most of them (except for *DI_nok1* and *DI_nok2*) lean slightly to the right, suggesting that modestly disruptive papers may be more common than slightly developing ones. The result agrees with Park et.al (2023) and Holst et.al (2024), though against with Wu et.al (2019). And it has been proven that the citation coverage of different datasets can lead to bias in the calculated values of disruption indexes (Ruan et.al, 2021).

Figure 3: The value distribution of the Disruption index and its variants.

We also investigate the trend of the average value of each index over time (**Figure 4**). Most variables generally present a downward trend, indicating that science is becoming less disruptive over time both from an overall perspective and from the citing intentions of background, methodology and results comparison. And most variables show a significant decline since 1996, which may be attributed to a relatively increasing quality of metadata, e.g., the refinement of references and citations records in the dataset (Holst et.al, 2024). Additionally, the abnormal large mean values of the variables with intents, especially before 1996, may be due to the fact that the full text of early literature are inaccessible, thus few citations are labelled with intents. Besides, the patterns of the three original indexes are quite different from those of variants incorporating intents, which might confirm the value of reframing the disruption measures with citation intentions, to some extent.

Figure 4: The trend of average value over time for each disruption variant. The first row presents the results of encompassing all papers, while the second row shows the results of excluding papers with zero references.

3.2. Correlation among indexes of measuring disruption and citation impact

We further present the interconnections among the variables in the correlogram (**Figure 5**). Since the disruption indicators are not normally distributed, we calculate Spearman rank correlation instead of Pearson correlation. All coefficients are statistically significant given the large sample size. We interpret the coefficients according to Cohen (1988): small effect ($r = 0.1$), medium effect ($r = 0.3$), large effect ($r = 0.5$), and very large effect ($r = 0.7$).

As shown, the disruption variants incorporating intents generally correlate among themselves at a very high positive level, and correlate at medium positive level with the three original indexes, indicating convergent validity of the variants with intents. And high positive correlations coefficients are visible among DI , DI_nok1 and DI_nok2 ($r=0.90$, 0.90 , 1.00) since they load on one dimension. The same is true of indicators with intents: for those measuring background ($r=0.84$, 0.84 , 1.00), methodology ($r=0.76$, 0.76 , 1.00), and result comparison ($r=0.68$, 0.68 , 1.00).

Figure 5: Spearman rank correlations of indicators measuring disruption and citation.

4. Discussion and conclusion

It is widely acknowledged that references in a scientific article do not share the equal importance (Nicholson et.al, 2021; Roman et.al, 2021b), and citations in different sections of the citing paper have also been proven to possess distinct citing levels, with meaningful or high-intensity citations dominating sections of method, results, and discussion (Maričić et al., 1998). Therefore, when measuring science advances through the Disruption index and its variants, it could be problematic to solely utilize the count of citations without considering their contexts and intentions. Our study fills this gap and proposes a new set of disruption variants incorporating citation intents. We further calculate the values of these variants based on the S2AG dataset, and perform descriptive analysis and Spearman rank correlation for papers published from 1969 to 2019. The results show that the distribution of variants incorporating intents and the Disruption index *DI* all lean slightly to the right. And the different patterns observed in the average value trend between variants with intents and the original indexes affirm the value of reframing the disruptiveness in terms of different citation intents, while the positive correlation coefficients at the medium level between them also indicate the convergent validity of the variants with intents. Additionally, the decreasing average values of these variants over time present a less disruptive trend in science, which agrees with Park et.al (2023) and Holst et.al (2024) and may be attributed to the increased burden of knowledge (Jones, 2009) and the lack of “low-hanging fruit” (Cowen, 2001).

This study contributes to research evaluation by taking the intentions of authors’ citing behaviour into account, which allows for further understanding of the evolution of science progress. It is also beneficial to unveil more details of authors’ citing behaviours in scientific activities through deeply measuring their distinct efforts to frame the research work in different sections. The study also has several limitations. First, due to the availability of the full text of publications, only around 30% citations in the S2AG dataset have classified citation intents,

resulting in numerous data missing in the calculation of the variants incorporating intents. This will inevitably lead to a bias in our results. Second, the applicability and effectiveness of the variants with intents may require feasible assessment. Future study could invite experts to propose papers that make disruptive contributions in the three aspects to assess their validity. And since subjective judgments may introduce biases, it is also vital to evaluate the variants against gold-standard datasets that provide information on whether a paper contributes in methodology or results or theory.

Open science practices

In the study, we take use of the openly accessible data provided by the Semantic Scholar API (available at <https://www.semanticscholar.org/product/api>), which provides a reliable source of scholarly data to the public for free and thus makes a contribution to promoting scientific innovation and advancement. In addition, we also follow up on the latest research findings by referring to the preprints published on the arXiv (<https://arxiv.org/>), which provides open access to nearly 2.4 million academic papers for free. Furthermore, we also reported our preliminary research framework in a small seminar before the formal start of research work, and received many valuable suggestions, for which we would like to express our sincere gratitude.

Acknowledgments

We would like to thank Dr. Yi Bu for providing great help in data processing.

Author contributions

Xin Xie: Conceptualization, Methodology, Software, Data curation, Writing - original draft.

Jiang Li: Supervision, Conceptualization, Methodology, Writing - review & editing.

Competing interests

The authors declare no competing interests.

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